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A USER-CENTERED APPROACH TO SUPPORT UBIQUITOUS HEALTHCARE FOR PEDIATRIC CHRONIC ILLNESS

ASTHMA AS A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore design opportunities using ubiquitous computing healthcare systems for pediatric asthma patients and their primary caregivers. In this paper, we illustrate a rigorous process of user-centered design research that includes contextual interviews, concept refinement, and scenario development. Based on the empirical results and a theory of behavior change, we formed a three-stage design framework for healthcare: detection, behavior plan, and compliance. This process is essential in order to maintain constant and consistent asthma management. Our results also lead us to conceptualize and develop the Asthma Bag for Life Enhancement (ABLE). The ABLE system supports children and their caregivers' daily routines to improve asthma management strategies that lead to better health outcomes.

Keywords: User-centered design, Family, Health

INTRODUCTION

To improve the quality of the human health, many researchers and designers have actively explored healthcare information technologies. For example, computing technologies help manage chronic diseases by integrating personal healthcare records, monitoring patients, and supporting tele-health and telemedicine systems. By taking a user-centered approach, design opportunities for chronic disease management (e.g., for cancer and diabetes) have been proposed in human computer interaction and healthcare related domains (Hayes et al., 2008; C. M. Johnson, T. R. Johnson, & Zhang, 2005; Mamykina, E. Mynatt, Davidson, & Greenblatt, 2008). However, there is limited design research that has

investigated the systematic understanding of how users engage with healthcare technologies (Xue, Yen, Boucharenc, & Choolani, 2008). This is unfortunate since user-centered design can support users' needs and their natural interaction with systems (Norman, 1990). In addition, previous work has relatively failed to consider the role of behavior change theory into the design process for designers. We believe that the latter will help enhance the interdisciplinary nature of the user-centered design, which has been found useful for supporting the self-management of chronic illnesses (Torsi, Nasr, Wright, Mawson, & Mountain, 2009).

Chronic illness requires constant management (always and everywhere). Thus, this study aims to explore opportunities for ubiquitous healthcare technologies through a user-centered research approach by looking at pediatric asthma as a case study. Asthma is a chronic respiratory disease that causes coughing, wheezing, and difficulty with breathing. It is a heterogeneous disease, and various psychological and environmental triggers affect different patients. There are two major reasons why we selected pediatric asthma as a case study. First, it is one of the most common childhood chronic diseases in the world (Masoli, Fabian, Holt, & Beasley, 2004). Second, pediatric asthma takes its toll on the whole family. This is the case because all members of the family must share the burden of being aware of the child's triggers and are responsible for caring for the child when their symptoms are exacerbated (Gallo, Breitmayer, Knafl, & Zoeller, 1991). For example, in the US, pediatric asthma is the leading cause of missed days of school (Tinkelman & Schwartz, 2004) and this translates to missed days of work for the parents. In fact, 44% of

parents reported missing work due to their child's illness (Diette & Rand, 2007).

In summary, the purpose of this study is to explore how a user-centered research approach can contribute to designing ubiquitous healthcare technologies for families who most care for a child with asthma. Since we were interested in understanding the nature of family-centered care for chronic illness, we set out to answer two research questions related to pediatric asthma management:

- What are challenges experienced by the family members of pediatric asthma patients?
- Where are the design opportunities for ubiquitous healthcare in supporting the everyday management of this chronic disease?

We also present three other design research contributions in this work. First, we want to expand the current understanding of the daily struggles experienced by the families of chronically ill pediatric patients. Second, we propose a design framework for health behavior change by explicitly presenting the relationship between empirical results and design opportunities. This leads to a unique process where design implications are drawn from both theory and data. Also, by illustrating a concrete design prototype, we hope to point out a connection between challenges in practice and design opportunities in this research. We begin by reviewing existing studies of asthma management and describe our design study process. Finally, we propose design implications and a final design prototype.

RELATED WORK

The clinical literature in pediatric asthma management indicates several design challenges in managing asthma due to heterogeneity of asthma (Lara, Akinbami, Flores, & Morgenstern, 2006; Valerio et al., 2006). For example, asthma is highly related to race, ethnicity, urban area, and socioeconomic levels. Additionally, there are at least three types of asthma triggers: environmental, physical, and psychological. Another well-known challenge is that often parents and children with asthma report different symptoms (Lara et al., 1998). Thus, active discussions related to asthma

care focus on complex issues such as how to avoid complicated asthma triggers, how to take medicines at the right time, and how to encourage patients to self-manage their asthma symptoms.

To address these issues, many researchers in clinical fields have developed healthcare applications such as internet-based systems and mobile phone diaries to support asthma management (Anhøj & Møldrup, 2004; Finkelstein, O'Connor, & Friedmann, 2001; Fiz, 2002). For example, short message services in mobile phones can warn patients about poor outdoor air quality (Chu, Huang, Lian, & Tsai, 2006). However, these technologies are limited by the fact that they focus on clinicians' perspectives rather than pediatric patients and their families' contexts. Thus, it is important to design appropriate healthcare applications by taking a user-centered design approach and paying attention to the needs of children with asthma and their parents in their everyday lives (Yun, Jeong, Lee, Arriaga, & Abowd, 2010). In particular, we argue that ubiquitous healthcare technologies based on user-centered design process with empirical studies and systematic analysis will provide the correct support.

DESIGN PROCESS AND METHODS

To investigate the needs of ubiquitous healthcare technologies, our research followed a user-centered design process including:

- Field observation
- Contextual interviews at the homes of nine families: ten children with asthma and their nine caregivers
- Interviews with six-healthcare providers
- Qualitative data analysis
- Integration of findings into a behavior change theoretical framework
- Design concept generation and refinement
- Final design

We first conducted exploratory fieldwork to further define our scope of inquiry and develop our interview guidelines (Figure 1). Then, we performed field observations at a doctor's office and public

parents need a better way of monitoring and identifying asthma triggers to prevent asthma symptoms and attacks that can cause a serious life-threatening situation.

ENCOURAGING SELF-MANAGEMENT

Asthma is a chronic disease that children have to deal with their whole life, so parents strongly desire that their children know how to manage the symptoms for themselves. Independent and self-monitoring of symptoms was particularly important for parents that worked. More specifically, caregivers wanted children to understand how to prevent asthma attacks, to know what to do when it flared up, and to be able to balance between performing physical exercises and preventing asthma symptoms. In our interviews, seven caregivers encouraged their children to make self-management be a part of their daily routine by emphasizing to-do-list repeatedly.

“We teach time and consistency measures, which is something that’s a work in progress... things like, ‘When you go in the bathroom, you have to use your Advair, you have to rinse your mouth. Put it by your toothbrush so that way you know how to use it.’”
(Mother of a nine year-old girl)

However, it is difficult for parents to encourage children to engage in self-management when they are away from the parents’ control. Children with asthma want to act like healthy children instead of limiting their activities even when they are aware that their behavior could lead to an asthma attack. For example, patients are told to seize playing sports when they feel asthma symptoms but often neglect to do so because they want to be a part of a group.

“I just keep running like I don’t even feel it... If I keep running it just calms down.” (11 year-old boy)

However, this behavior can cause asthma symptoms and make a child’s asthma get worse. Thus, families need support to encourage pediatric patients to manage their asthma voluntarily.

ADHERING TO MEDICATION REGIMENTS

Asthma medications regiments are complicated since there are at least two different kinds of medications that are commonly prescribed; a control (or maintenance) medicine for preventing asthma symptoms and a rescue medicine for emergency situation like asthma attack.

“Sometimes it’s a little difficult to get people to understand the difference between a maintenance medicine and a rescue medicine... a lot of times they still get their medicines mixed up.” (Physician assistant)

In addition, it is important for children with asthma to have an asthma action plan that categorizes a child’s asthma status into three levels: green (no asthma symptoms), yellow (mild to moderate symptoms), and red (severe symptoms) zones. Based on these three zones, the asthma action plan describes three different medicine treatments and actions that a child should take. All caregivers in our interviews usually remember the content of the asthma action plan, but only two children knew about the plans. Caregivers stated that they want to ensure that children can take appropriate medicines based on the plan even when the child is outside of their care (e.g., school or a relative’s homes).

To support children’s medication management, all families in our study had bags or boxes specifically designated for asthma medicines. Within the box, we saw ready-made plastic bags with asthma medicines for children. The designated storage made it easy for children to know where the medicine was and to take it around wherever they went.

“I have these bags here and I just put it in here, it has the name of the medicine, so they know it’s theirs. So, I put everything in here with the pamphlet, everything, and this is how they go. This bag has to go with them everywhere if they’re not going to be at home. This is their lifeline.” (Mother of four boys with asthma)

However, just having these bags around was insufficient for families to manage the complex medication regiments because there was no reliable

way to confirm whether the medicine was taken appropriately. As a result, parents explained that they often missed daily doses or had the child take multiple doses in one day.

“I forgot to give him his medicine yesterday, because we were on the go so much... I feel like the world’s worst mom... Sometimes there’s been times I’ve given him his inhaler more than what I’m supposed to.” (Mother of a 7 year-old boy with asthma)

This implies that asthma management requires that families not only have an action plan and the medicine readily available but also a reminder of when the medicine was administered.

DESIGN IMPLICATIONS FOR BEHAVIOR CHANGE

Our findings reveal three major themes that cause challenges in pediatric asthma management: identifying asthma triggers, encouraging self-management, and adhering to medication regimens. We now reframe these findings with our own asthma management phase to propose design implications. Our findings point toward the insight that behavior changes are critical for better asthma management. For example, while the purpose of identifying asthma trigger is to avoid triggers, encouraging self-management aims to modify a child’s behavior. In chronic disease management, the Transtheoretical Model and Stages of Change has been widely adopted for addictive health behavior changes (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997). The flow of stages in the model inspired us to reexamine special characteristics of asthma and its management phases. Thus, we create a design framework for health behavior change that describes our own asthma management phases to provide design implications systematically: Detection phase (recognizing what is going on) - behavior plan phase (modifying behaviors) - compliance phase (ascertaining what behavior was performed). This is an attempt to bridge a gap between the findings and design opportunities through a design framework (Figure 2).

Figure 2. A design framework of health behavior change

We describe each phase in context of pediatric asthma management identified in our own study and other literature. And then, we highlight design implications to better support each phase.

DETECTION: MONITORING ASTHMA TRIGGERS

The first phase in our asthma management scheme is the detection phase, which is related to “identifying asthma triggers.” Our study shows that asthma management often becomes an ad hoc process because people do not have the knowledge of what can cause the asthma attacks. It takes time to identify the triggers for a given individual. Triggers are often identified during consultations with professions who help individuals to reflect on past asthmatic episodes. However, there is pressure to learn the individual triggers quickly, because even one asthmatic episode can lead to a critical condition for the child.

To support this reflection and learning process, we propose the use of automated capture and access techniques to monitor and record the details surrounding an episode and support an individual in reexamining those details (G. D. Abowd & E. D. Mynatt, 2000). For example, it is necessary for technology design researchers to explore capture systems to support reflection by providing a family with a range of instruments (e.g., indoor air quality meters), and monitoring the readings from these devices. The recorded indoor data becomes automatically paired with outdoor air quality. Caregivers can access these recordings as needed, and reflect on how their children’s asthma connected to both indoor and outdoor air qualities.

To improve the applicability of this design, there must be portable sensors and customizable features. First, the ubiquitous healthcare technology needs to monitor real-time triggers for asthma such as pollen, temperature and humidity because children react to multiple triggers at different places, and they vary among individuals. Currently, one short messaging service system exists, which sends an alert for severe ozone level in a selected area (by ZIP code) (Chu et al., 2006). However, we contend that measuring air quality by zip code may be too broad and does not

accurately reflect conditions surrounding the children's location. Therefore, the instrument needs to deploy a sufficiently dense array of sensors that can provide updated information for an individual. In a word, the instrument should sense air quality in a close proximity to a child. We propose wearable or portable sensors that possibly look similar to small clips or necklaces. This way, the system can easily capture and monitor the air quality that surrounds the child.

Second, the design should support customizable sensing to allow for variations in lifestyle such as individuals living with carpeting or pets. Customization also plays an important role because the environment that surrounds a child may change, and the triggers themselves appear and disappear over time. In this study, we found that the caregivers expressed difficulties in identifying the changing triggers (e.g., different triggers at various places). That says, the healthcare technology should not only support customization of sensing, but also record sensing modalities to display comprehensive information on the trends and ease the cognitive burden of families. For example, giving a visual cue such as a flashing light can help families easily perceive current environmental information.

BEHAVIOR PLAN: SETTING GOALS FOR DAILY ACTIONS

The second phase for our asthma management system is a behavior plan that indicates setting a goal for behavior modification. The finding in our study highlights the importance of self-management among asthmatic children. As described before, since asthma is a disease that children have to deal with for their entire life, caregivers strongly desire that their children know how to manage their asthma. In this behavior plan phase, caregivers can encourage their children to change behaviors by providing goals for daily actions.

For example, setting daily goals can motivate children to modify their behaviors based on asthma action plans. With older children, healthcare providers also use the asthma action plans to help children change their behaviors for better asthma management.

While the asthma action plan provides the personalized medical treatment information, an asthma slide rule recommends possible physical activities that an asthma patient can engage in during a given level of air pollution (Reischl & Colby, 2007). This asthma slide rule is useful to help children learn what the relationship is between their current symptoms, outdoor air quality and activity level. Two major design implications arise in setting a goal-based action plan and the asthma slide rule: information retrieval and self-management recommendation.

For these features, context awareness provides a great solution since it can collect personalized information such as physical and emotional state. For example, context awareness system combined with an asthma action plan and asthma slide rule can help caregivers supervise children properly, reduce the caregiver burden, and reinforce independent management. Since children are easily distracted by contextual information (e.g., physical environment, social relation, and emotional state) (Norman, 1990), setting appropriate goals based on various contexts would encourage children to follow self-management and to be more aware of their asthma. To design child-friendly healthcare technology, graphical or animated images for setting daily goals might be useful.

COMPLIANCE: REVIEWING MEDICATION SCHEDULES

The last phase is compliance. In the compliance phase, families want to know if their asthmatic children take their medicine daily. In addition, healthcare providers always emphasize the importance of taking the proper medication dosage. Thus, this compliance phase concerns reviewing the medication schedules.

To assure that this information is available to the child, parents currently use their own "asthma bags" including the relevant instructions. Namely, these bags are placed in various locations so that the child can readily access them. In fact, smart bags have been suggested for busy families in supporting their daily activities and memories on necessary items (M. K. Lee, Davidoff, J. Zimmerman, & Dey, 2007; Park & John Zimmerman, 2010). Thus, asthma medicine

bags observed in our home visit interviews can serve to optimize mobility and accessibility of the medication and instructions. However, caregivers cannot always ensure that their child knows how to take their medicine and even the parents explained that they could not remember if their child already took the medications.

Thus, to review current medication status and increase accuracy of taking the medicines, ubiquitous healthcare technology could be embedded in the bags. The system may include auto-capture recording and reminders about a child's asthma medication status. This would help families retrieve and confirm the medication schedule and information. This ubiquitous reviewing system in bags for pediatric asthma management can be one of promising design solutions in the compliance phase since bags are everyday artifacts and easily shared by all family members.

DESIGN CONCEPT REFINEMENT

Before we conducted home visit interviews, one of our interview goals was to refine our initial concept on ubiquitous healthcare applications. Based on existing research related to families with pediatric asthma, we came up with one initial and abstract ubiquitous healthcare technology design concept, a portable device that includes features such as asthma symptom input and environmental trigger notification. In the interviews, caregivers expressed that a mobile phone can be a potential solution for our concept, but only two children had mobile phones. During the interviews with families and healthcare providers, we explained our initial concept briefly and received feedback on the concept.

Based on the feedback from the interviewees, we refined our concept with two design requirements. First, the information in a portable device must be personalized since asthma is a very personalized disease, and every patient has different treatments. Second, a portable device should be a child-friendly and could be potentially shared by all caregivers who can assist children in managing asthma. Finally, we created our design prototype in supporting

ubiquitous healthcare for families with pediatric asthma: ABLE - Asthma Bag for Life Enhancement.

DESIGN PROTOTYPE: ABLE

Based on findings and design implications, we propose one design prototype, ABLE - Asthma Bag for Life Enhancement. ABLE is a smart bag that supports ubiquitous asthma management for pediatric patients and their family

ASTHMA BAG FOR LIFE ENHANCEMENT (ABLE)

The ABLE system consists of five parts: the main asthma bag, portable environmental sensors, asthma action plan, asthma medicine tools, and text messaging service in mobile phones. Figure 3 shows the ABLE system diagram (Figure 3).

First, the main asthma bag is in the center of the ABLE system because it displays environmental trigger status, the daily action plan, and medical regimen. Since children can carry the bag everywhere, it can capture a child's physical and social context focused on asthma triggers, symptoms, and activity schedule. Based on the information that the bag displays, children can be more aware of their asthma status, and parents can focus on encouraging children to take the right actions for better asthma management. The information displayed on the bag comes from four major items that include portable environmental sensors, asthma action plan, a caregiver's mobile phone, and asthma medicine tools.

Second, portable environmental sensors are important for families to capture current ongoing air quality. The sensors can be embedded in the bag with the ABLE system, and send current air quality information to a special fabric on a bag cover. The bag cover fabric can display the air quality information through a lighting color. For example, while green color can represent good air quality status, red color can represent bad air quality status.

Third, the asthma action plan can play an important role in supporting daily actions for children since it includes actions children should take according to their symptoms. This action plan can be enhanced by the asthma slide rule that provides possible physical

Figure 3. ABLÉ system diagram

activities that the child can engage in according to current air quality information. Since the action plan can be connected to the ABLÉ system, possible current actions can be suggested on a front pocket display on the bag. For example, during a “green” air quality day, a graphical image of a variety of activities appears to indicate the child can go outside and play, and during a “red” day the graphical icon can denote that the child should not play outside. The general idea is that simply viewing the pocket display can motivate the child to change their behavior.

Fourth, given that a child’s asthma status may change from day to day the caregiver must be able to program this into ABLÉ. We propose that the caregiver can input a child’s asthma status (e.g., mild, moderate, or severe) through a mobile phone interface that is connected to the bag. The application allows a caregiver to input the asthma status through a text messaging service that transfers the information to the bag. After receiving a child’s asthma status information from the

application, the bag can display recommended actions in the front pocket so that a child (or other caregivers) can know possible actions. Multiple caregivers could be authorized to access this interface so that they can update and share the child’s status as needed. For example, the child may be fine in the morning but can develop a cough during physical activity. The teacher would then be able to update the child’s status so that the after-school caregiver can be made aware of the change. In addition, this interface can also allow the caregivers to retrieve information about the child (e.g., medication status).

Fifth, asthma medicines can be monitored by the ABLÉ system in the bag so that families can review current asthma medicine status. In general, patients with asthma can take asthma medicine through inhalers. Some digital inhalers have counter features so that users can monitor current medicine status. Thus, medicine status information from the inhalers can be transferred to the bag and displayed in an interactive bag charm with child-friendly

Findings	Design Implications	Design Features in ABLE	Relevant phases
Identifying asthma triggers	Monitoring asthma triggers	Ambient light with trigger sensors	Detection
Encouraging self-management	Setting goals for daily actions	Display for recommended actions	Behavior plan
Adhering to medication	Reviewing medication schedules	Interactive charm for medication	Compliance

Table 1. A relationship between themes and relevant phases in designing ABLE

visualization. By showing different levels of a graphical image, children can review their medication status, and caregivers can encourage children to increase their self-management.

DESIGN FEATURES AND SCENARIOS

There are three major design features related to findings and design implications. Each design feature has a relationship with each finding and design implication (Table 1). To address how we applied this design research to practical design prototype, we developed three scenarios that support each asthma management phase.

Ambient light with trigger sensors (Detection)

- A family goes to a park for a picnic and outdoor activities.
- The mom prepares the asthma bag for her eight year-old son's asthma medicines.
- When the family plays Frisbee in the park, the bag beeps and its cover with ambient light becomes red to indicate that the current air quality in this park is hazardous.
- The family decides to play inside the park gym instead so that the boy can avoid the asthma trigger and prevent symptoms.

Display for recommended actions (Behavior plan)

- In the morning, the ABLE system sends a text message to mom asking her son's asthma status.
- She replies to the message by inputting the information that her son's asthma is moderate today.
- Based on her reply and current air quality from environmental sensors, the ABLE system displays graphical images of possible activities such as moderate biking and easy gymnastics on the front pocket of the bag.

- In the afternoon, the son checks the images on the pocket and bikes with friends at the playground.

Interactive charm for medication reminders (Compliance)

- The mom gives the asthma bag to her son before he goes to school.
- The interactive charm in the bag shows today's asthma medicine schedule with one flashing orange colored light. It indicates that he should take 2 puffs of the inhaler before a physical exercise class at 2pm.
- The charm beeps and flashes again around 2pm, and he takes the asthma medicine before the class. Once the blue tooth device registers that the canister has been pressed 4 times a signal is transmitted to the charm. The charm then turns green to indicate that he has taken his medicine. (This information can also be transmitted via SMS to her.)
- In the evening, all family members can review today's asthma medicine status together by looking at the charm.

CONCLUSION

This study explores opportunities for ubiquitous healthcare technologies to support pediatric asthma patients and their family. In this paper, our design research contributes to design communities in three ways. First, we provide insights on potential opportunities for design research in supporting the needs of pediatric patients and their families. Second, we show the relevance of tying the findings to a domain specific theory of behavior change. We then systematically draw implications for how each step of the behavior change model can be complemented with ubiquitous technology. This culminates in the development of a technology that supports the family's efforts to manage pediatric

asthma and encourage the child's long-term self-management.

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REFERENCE

- Abowd, G. D., & Mynatt, E. D. (2000). Charting past, present, and future in Ubiquitous Computing. *Transactions on {Computer-Human} Interaction*, 7(1), 29-58.
- Anhøj, J., & Møldrup, C. (2004). Feasibility of collecting diary data from asthma patients through mobile phones and SMS (short message service): response rate analysis and focus group evaluation from a pilot study. *J Med Internet Res.*, 6(4), e42.
- Chu, H.-T., Huang, C.-C., Lian, Z.-H., & Tsai, J. J. P. (2006). A ubiquitous warning system for asthma-inducement. *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Sensor Networks, Ubiquitous, and Trustworthy Computing*. Washington, DC, USA: IEEE Computer Society.
- Diette, G. B., & Rand, C. (2007). The contributing role of health-care communication to health disparities for minority patients with asthma. *Chest*, 132(5), 802S-809S. doi: 10.1378/chest.07-1909.
- Finkelstein, J., O'Connor, G., & Friedmann, R. H. (2001). Development and implementation of the home asthma telemonitoring (HAT) system to facilitate asthma self-care. *Studies in health technology and informatics*, 84(Pt 1), 810-4. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11604847>.
- Fiz, J. a. (2002). Detection of Wheezing During Maximal Forced Exhalation in Patients With Obstructed Airways*. *Chest*, 122(1), 186-191. doi: 10.1378/chest.122.1.186.
- Gallo, A. M., Breitmayer, B. J., Knafl, K. A., & Zoeller, L. H. (1991). Stigma in childhood chronic illness: a well sibling perspective. *Pediatric Nursing Journal*, 17(1), 21-5.
- Hayes, G. R., Abowd, G. D., Davis, J. S., Blount, M. L., Ebling, M., & Mynatt, E. D. (2008). Opportunities for Pervasive Computing in Chronic Cancer Care. *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Pervasive Computing*. ACM Press.
- Johnson, C. M., Johnson, T. R., & Zhang, J. (2005). A user-centered framework for redesigning health care interfaces. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 38(1), 75-87.
- Lara, M., Akinbami, L., Flores, G., & Morgenstern, H. (2006). Heterogeneity of childhood asthma among hispanic children: Puerto Rican children bear a disproportionate burden. *Pediatrics*, 117(1), 43-53.
- Lara, M., Duan, N., Sherbourne, C., Lewis, M. A., Landon, C., Halfon, N., et al. (1998). Differences Between Child and Parent Reports of Symptoms Among Latino Children With Asthma. *Pediatrics*, 102(6), e68.
- Lee, M. K., Davidoff, S., Zimmerman, J., & Dey, A. K. (2007). Smart bag: Managing home and raising children. *Proceedings of the 2007 International Conference on Designing Pleasurable Products and Interfaces* (pp. 434-437). ACM Press.
- Mamykina, L., Mynatt, E., Davidson, P., & Greenblatt, D. (2008). MAHI: investigation of social scaffolding for reflective thinking in diabetes management. *Proceeding of the twenty-sixth annual SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems* (p. 477-486). ACM. Retrieved December 1, 2010, from <http://portal.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1357054.1357131>.
- Masoli, M., Fabian, D., Holt, S., & Beasley, R. (2004). The global burden of asthma: executive summary of the GINA dissemination committee report. *Allergy*, 59, 469-478.
- Norman, D. (1990). *The Design of Everyday Things*. NY: Doubleday.
- Park, S. Y., & Zimmerman, John. (2010). Investigating the Opportunity for a Smart Activity Bag. *Proceeding of the twenty-eighth annual CHI conference on Human factors in computing systems - CHI '10* (pp. 2543-2552). ACM Press.
- Prochaska, J. O., & Velicer, W. F. (1997). The transtheoretical model of health behavior change. *American journal of health promotion*, 12(1), 38-48.
- Reischl, U., & Colby, C. (2007). Asthma Slide Rule: A Tool for Managing a Child's Physical Activity During Air Pollution Episodes.
- Segelstrom, F., Holmlid, S., & Alm, B. (2009). Back to the Roots: A Case for a New Ideal for Ethnographic Research for Design. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Association of Societies of Design Research, IASDR 2009, Rigor and Relevance in Design*. Seoul, Korea.
- Tinkelman, D., & Schwartz, A. (2004). School-Based Asthma Disease Management. *Journal of Asthma*, 41(4), 455-462.
- Torsi, S., Nasr, N., Wright, P. C., Mawson, S. J., & Mountain, G. A. (2009). User-centered design for supporting the self-management of chronic illnesses: an interdisciplinary approach. *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments*. ACM Press.
- Valerio, M., Cabana, M. D., White, D. F., Heidmann, D. M., Brown, R. W., & Bratton, S. L. (2006). Understanding of asthma management: Medicaid parents' perspectives. *Chest*, 129(3), 594-601. doi: 10.1378/chest.129.3.594.
- Xue, L., Yen, C. C., Boucharenc, C., & Choolani, M. (2008). The design evolution of medical devices: moving from object to user. *Journal of Design Research*, 7(4), 411-438.
- Yun, T. J., Jeong, H. Y., Lee, H. R., Arriaga, R., & Abowd, G. (2010). Assessing asthma management practices through in-home technology probes. *Pervasive Health 2010* (p. 1-9). IEEE. Retrieved December 28, 2010, from http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpls/abs_all.jsp?arnumber=5482301.